

Molybdate assisted ninhydrin based spectrophotometric method for the estimation of Metformin hydrochloride in bulk drugs and tablet dosage form

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Abstract : This paper describes an accurate, precise and economical spectrophotometric method for the determination of Metformin hydrochloride in bulk drugs and tablet dosage form. The analysis is based on the reaction of Metformin hydrochloride (primary amino group) reacts with ninhydrin and ammonium molybdate mixture to give Ruhemann's purple product with maximum absorbance (λ_{\max}) at 570 nm. The effects of variables such as temperature, heating time, concentration of colour producing reagent and stability of colour were investigated to optimize the procedure. This reaction proceeds quantitatively at 90 ± 1 °C in 10 min. Beer-Lambert's law is obeyed in the concentration range of 10–30 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and is described by the regression equation $Y = 0.061x - 0.125$ with a regression coefficient (r^2) = 0.997 ($n = 5$). For Metformin hydrochloride, the value of molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity are 9.490×10^3 L/mol/cm and 0.0174 $\mu\text{g/cm}^2$, respectively and of LOD and LOQ are found to be 1.6373 and 4.9616 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, respectively. The statistically validated results indicate that the proposed method has good sensitivity, accuracy, precision and stability. The method is eco-friendly and economic as it does not involve any organic solvents. The developed method was successfully applied for the determination of Metformin hydrochloride in bulk powder and tablet dosage form.

Keywords : Metformin hydrochloride, ninhydrin, ammonium molybdate, spectrophotometry.

Introduction

Metformin hydrochloride^{1,2} is chemically, 1-carbamimidamido-*N,N*-dimethylmethanimidamide (Fig. 1). It is white crystalline powder, hygroscopic and freely soluble in water. It is an oral anti-diabetic drug from the

Fig. 1. Structure of Metformin hydrochloride (MET).

biguanide class. It is the first-line drug for the treatment of type-II diabetes, particularly in overweight and obese people and those with normal kidney function and evidence suggests it may be the best choice for people with heart failure. It is also used in the treatment of polycystic

ovary syndrome. Metformin hydrochloride decreases hepatic glucose production, decreases intestinal absorption of glucose and improves insulin sensitivity by increasing peripheral glucose uptake and utilization. Major action of Metformin hydrochloride is increasing glucose transport across the cell membrane in skeletal muscle³.

The literature survey has revealed that various methods are available for estimation of Metformin hydrochloride alone and in combination with other drugs. The reported methods available are spectrophotometry^{4–19}, spectrofluorimetry²⁰, HPLC^{21–25}, UPLC²⁶, HPTLC^{27,28} and capillary electrophoresis²⁹ and for its estimation alone and combination with other drug in pharmaceutical dosage forms.

To the best of author's knowledge, there are few visible spectrophotometric methods for the estimation of Metformin hydrochloride³⁰. The analysis is based on the reaction of Metformin hydrochloride (primary amino group) reacts with ninhydrin and ammonium molybdate

mixture to give Ruhemann's purple product³¹. Thus, the present work describes the development and validation of a new spectrophotometric method for estimation of Metformin hydrochloride in bulk and tablet dosage form.

Visible spectrophotometry is the technique of choice even today because of its inherent simplicity, sensitivity, selectivity, accuracy, precision and cost-effectiveness. The recent development of new analytical method with good characteristics such as selectivity and sensitivity are not only sufficient but also fulfils the green analytical approaches^{32,33}. Hence, the purpose of the present study was to improve this method with respect to two experimental objectives : (i) decrease the heating time, (ii) avoid the use of organic solvent. Both factors are of great significance in reducing time and cost of analysis.

Materials and method :

Apparatus :

A Shimadzu 1800 double beam UV-Vis spectrophotometer provided with 1 cm matched quartz cell was used for absorbance measurements.

Reagents and chemicals :

Metformin hydrochloride was obtained as gift sample from Wockhardt Pharmaceuticals Pvt. Ltd. (Aurangabad, India). All other reagents used were of analytical grade.

Preparation of citrate buffer of pH 5.5 :

21.0 g of citric acid dissolved in 200 ml 1.0 M NaOH in distilled water and made up to 1000 ml with distilled water.

Preparation of ninhydrin solution :

0.44 g of ninhydrin was dissolved in 25 ml citrate buffer of pH 5.5.

Preparation of ammonium molybdate :

6.1 g of ammonium molybdate was dissolved in 25 ml citrate buffer of pH 5.5.

Preparation of standard solution of MET :

10 mg pure Metformin hydrochloride was transferred to 100 ml volumetric flask and diluted upto the mark with distilled water to get a concentration of 100 µg/ml solution.

Optimized procedure :

In a 10 ml volumetric flask, add 2.0 ml standard stock solution (100 µg/ml), 1.0 ml ninhydrin and 1.0 ml satu-

rated ammonium molybdate solution and diluted upto the mark with citrate buffer pH 5.5 (20 µg/ml). It was heated in boiling water bath at 90 ± 1 °C in 10 min and cooled to room temperature. Scan the spectrum and absorbance was measured λ_{max} at 570 nm versus the reagent blank (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Spectrum of Metformin hydrochloride (MET).

Method validation³⁴ :

Stability :

In order to demonstrate the stability of the Ninhydrin-Metformin hydrochloride complex in presence of saturated ammonium molybdate solution was analyzed over a period of 12 h at room temperature. During analysis, the complex was found to be stable over a period of 8 h at room temperature as shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Effect of time (min) on absorbance of MET-ninhydrin complex.

Linearity :

From the standard stock solution (100 µg/ml), different aliquots (1.0, 1.5, 2.0, 2.5 and 3.0) were taken in a

series of 10 ml volumetric flasks and 1.0 ml ninhydrin was added to it followed by 1.0 ml saturated ammonium molybdate solution and volume made up with citrate buffer pH 5.5 to get concentration 10–30 µg/ml. All flasks were heated for 10 min in boiling water bath and cooled to room temperature and measure the absorbance at 570 nm. Five replicates of analytes were measured and record the absorbance versus concentration as shown in Table 1. Plot a graph concentration versus absorbance; a linear correlation was found which obeys Beer-Lambert’s law in the concentration range of 10–30 µg/ml (Fig. 4). Regression analysis of Beer’s law data using the method of least squares was made to evaluate the slope (*b*), intercept (*a*) and the correlation coefficient (*r*²).

Table 1. Observation table for calibration curve of Metformin hydrochloride

Concentration (µg/ml)	Absorbance
10	0.471
15	0.81
20	1.157
25	1.41
30	1.719

Fig. 4. Calibration curve of Metformin hydrochloride (MET).

Limit of detection (LOD) and limit of quantification (LOQ) :

The detection limit of an individual analytical procedure is the lowest amount of analyte in a sample that can be detected but not necessarily quantitated as an exact value. The quantitation limit of an individual analytical procedure is the lowest amount of analyte in a sample that can be quantitatively determined with suitable precision and accuracy. The value of LOD and LOQ are de-

termined by using standard deviation of the response and slope approach as defined in International Conference on Harmonization (ICH) guidelines and given in Table 2.

Table 2. Optical characteristics data and validation parameters of Metformin hydrochloride

Parameter	Analytical data
Linearity range (µg/ml)	10–30
λ_{max} (nm)	570
Molar extinction coefficient (L/mol/cm)	9.490×10^3
Sandell’s sensitivity (µg/cm ²)	0.0174
Slope	6.10×10^{-2}
Intercept	-0.125
Standard deviation about regression (<i>S_y</i>)	± 0.1642
Standard deviation of slope (<i>S_b</i>)	± 0.0103
Standard deviation of intercept (<i>S_a</i>)	± 0.2203
Correlation coefficient (<i>r</i>)	0.997
Limit of detection (LOD, µg/ml)	1.6373
Limit of quantification (LOQ, µg/ml)	4.9616

Precision :

To determine precision, 7 days measurement (intra-days and inter-day) were computed with relative standard deviation (RSD%) for replicate samples (*n* = 5) using concentration 10, 15 and 20 µg/ml, both the intra-day and inter-day samples were calibrated with standard curve concurrently prepared in the same day of analysis as mention in Table 3.

Table 3. Evaluation of intra-day and inter-day accuracy and precision

MET taken (µg/ml)	Intra-day accuracy and precision			Inter-day accuracy and precision		
	MET found (µg/ml)	RE%	RSD%	MET found (µg/ml)	RE%	RSD%
10	10.0111	0.0936	0.9357	10.1533	0.1463	1.4416
15	15.0283	0.0735	0.4897	15.1233	0.2063	1.3645
20	20.0115	0.0909	0.4543	20.2550	0.3632	1.7933

Accuracy :

To determine the accuracy of the proposed method, recovery study was carried out by adding different amount (80%, 100%, 120%) of bulk sample of Metformin hydrochloride within the linearity range and results obtained are compiled in Table 4 and show good accuracy for the method.

Table 4. Recovery data

Level (%)	Amount of MET added (μg)	Amount of MET found (μg)	% Recovery	% RSD
80	18	18.14	100.77	0.6627
100	20	20.27	101.35	1.0841
120	22	22.31	101.40	1.4250

*An average value \pm relative standard deviation of 5 observations.

Assay :

Assay of tablet dosage form was carried by same procedure as mentioned in methodology to equivalent weight of Metformin hydrochloride by proposed spectrophotometric method. The percent purity was found out using regression analysis (Table 5).

Table 5. Assay results of tablet dosage form

Formulation	Actual amount (μg)	Amount Found (μg)	% of Drug Found
Tablet	10	10.21	102.1

Results and discussion

Preliminary studies were carried out to establish the optimum conditions for assay of the Metformin hydrochloride.

Effect of temperature :

The effect of temperature on the complexation reaction at 80, 90, 97 \pm 1 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ were examined (Table 6). It was observed that ninhydrin-MET complex in saturated ammonium molybdate required 90 \pm 1 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for obtaining maximum and stable absorbance and remained constant for about a further 8 h.

Table 6. Effect of temperature on absorbance

Temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	Absorbance
80 \pm 1	0.761
90 \pm 1	1.282
97 \pm 1	0.282

Effect of the reaction heating time :

The effect of time on the complexation reactions at room temperature was examined. It was observed that ninhydrin-MET charge transfer complex in saturated ammonium molybdate required 10 min for obtaining maximum and stable absorbance as shown in Fig. 5.

Effect of Heating Time

Fig. 5. Effect of the reaction heating time on absorbance.

Effect of reagents concentration :

The optimum conditions for the method was established by varying the concentration of reagent at a time and keeping the fixed drug concentration and observing the effect produced on the coloured species. To establish the optimum experimental condition for ninhydrin-MET charge transfer complex, the drug (20 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$) was allowed to react with varying volumes of 0.5% ninhydrin. The maximum absorbance was obtained with 1.0 ml of the reagent (Fig. 6); further addition caused no significant change in absorbance. Therefore a volume of 1.0 ml was used as an optimum value.

Effect of colouring agent

Fig. 6. Effect of volume of 0.5% ninhydrin on the absorbance of reaction product.

It was reported that in alkaline medium, ninhydrin is reduced to an intermediate, hydrindantin and converted to diketohydrindylidene diketohydrindamine which is commonly referred as 'Ruhemann's purple'. The primary amino group of Metformin hydrochloride reacted with

ninhydrin in presence of saturated ammonium molybdate solution (alkaline medium) to give diketohydrindylidene diketohydrindamine of Metformin hydrochloride reacts with ninhydrin via oxidation deamination of the primary amino group followed by the condensation of the reduced ninhydrin to form the colored Ruhemann's purple without employing any organic solvent, which absorbs a maximum at 570 nm as shown in Fig. 2. The proposed reaction between of Metformin hydrochloride and ninhydrin is shown in the Scheme 1.

To optimize the reaction conditions, different parameters have been investigated such as temperature, heating time, reagent concentration, and color stability. Reaction between ninhydrin and of Metformin hydrochloride did not give any colored product in the absence of ammonium molybdate, not even after prolonged heating. It was observed that complete colour development was attained at 90 ± 1 °C. The optimum reaction time was determined by heating the reaction mixture on a water bath at 90 ± 1 °C. It was noted that complete colour develop-

Scheme 1. Formation of Ruhemann's purple complex between MET and ninhydrin.

Table 7. Comparison between the proposed and published method³⁵

Parameters	Proposed method	Published method
Reagents	Citrate buffer pH 5.5 Ammonium molybdate 1 ml of 0.5% ninhydrin	Distilled water 1.5 ml 5 M NaOH 2.2 ml of 1% ninhydrin
Heating time (min)	10	30
Absorption maxima (λ_{\max})	570 nm	570 nm
Linearity ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	10–30	8–18
Stability of colour	8 h	15 min
Molar absorptivity (L/mol/cm)	9.490×10^3	5.7×10^3
Sandell's sensitivity ($\mu\text{g/cm}^2$)	0.0174	0.0175

ment was attained in ten minutes. The effect of ninhydrin concentration on the colour development was investigated. 1 ml of 0.5% ninhydrin reagent produced maximum colour intensity. Interestingly, reaction was found to be specific in ammonium molybdate medium.

The comparison between the proposed and published method was shown in Table 7.

Conclusion

From the result and discussion it can be concluded that spectrophotometric method has found to be an accurate, precise and economic for the determination of Metformin hydrochloride as comparison with published method (Table 7). The present modified method can be considered green as it demonstrates that visible spectrophotometry can be utilized without the usage of organic solvent. In addition, the proposed method employs an inexpensive instrument. Overall the proposed eco-friendly spectrophotometric method is economical and suitable for quality control of Metformin hydrochloride in bulk, fixed-dose combination tablets.

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